

EARLY DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS OF URINARY TUBULAR BIOMARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY

Mansurov M.R

Tashkent State Medical University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan ORCID

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9103-3358>

Mukhamedova N. Kh.

Tashkent State Medical University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6292-2428>

email address

nurhon6969@mail.ru

Abstract. *Diabetic nephropathy is a severe pathological condition caused by various etiological factors, leading to a decline in patients' quality of life. Currently, early detection of diabetic nephropathy, prediction of its progression, and timely recommendation of effective treatment methods are among the most pressing issues in medicine.*

Keywords: *diabetic nephropathy, monocyte chemoattractant protein, L-FABP, kidney injury molecule - KIM-1*

Introduction

Proteomic analysis is aimed at simultaneously studying numerous individual proteins, forming a system that characterizes the studied object as a whole [1,2]. The subject of proteomics includes the synthesis, modification, degradation, and transformation of proteins within the studied object [3,4,5,6].

During the destruction of epithelial cells in the proximal renal tubules, the synthesis of glycoprotein KIM-1 inhibits the development of autoimmune reactions. Thus, KIM-1 serves as a marker of kidney injury, significantly increasing on the apical membrane of proximal tubular epithelium upon damage. It remains elevated until tubular function is fully restored and is not observed thereafter, making it absent in healthy kidney tissues.

Objective

To evaluate the diagnostic value of urinary proteomic markers in the early diagnosis of diabetic nephropathy.

Materials and Methods

The study included 58 patients aged 40–55 years diagnosed with diabetic nephropathy, treated in 2023 at the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical

(6th international scientific and practical conference)

Academy and its endocrinology and nephrology departments. A control group consisted of 18 healthy individuals.

Clinical, biochemical, immunoassay, mass spectrometry, and statistical analysis methods were employed

Discussion of Results

The results of the study (see table) show that the level of kidney injury molecule KIM-1 in urine among patients with diabetic nephropathy was $2.56 \pm 1.28 \mu\text{g/mL}$, which is significantly higher—approximately twice—than in the control group ($0.83 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

Compared to healthy individuals without renal pathology, urinary KIM-1 levels were elevated threefold.

In our study, urinary levels of liver-type fatty acid-binding protein (L-FABP) increased to $8.4 \pm 0.78 \mu\text{g/g}$ due to enhanced excretion from proximal tubules in patients with diabetic nephropathy.

Table 1

Indicators of Urinary Tubular Biomarkers in Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy (M±m)

Indicators	Control Group (n=18)	Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy (n=58)
KIM-1 in urine ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	0.83 ± 0.07	$2.56 \pm 1.28^*$
Monocyte Chemoattractant Protein-1 (pg/mg creatinine)	1.14 ± 0.13	$6.87 \pm 0.59^*$
L-FABP in urine ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	1.86 ± 0.17	$8.4 \pm 0.78^*$

In all patients with diabetic nephropathy based on chronic kidney failure, urinary MCP-1 levels were significantly higher ($6.87 \pm 0.59 \text{ pg/mg}$) than in healthy individuals.

A direct and statistically significant correlation was found between urinary MCP-1 levels and creatinine. In patients with nephrosclerosis due to chronic pyelonephritis, elevated urinary MCP-1 excretion was observed.

The role of MCP-1 as a key chemokine functioning primarily in the interstitial region is confirmed by its maximal levels and the predominance of glomerular fibrosis.

Detection of profibrogenic cytokines MCP-1 and L-FABP in urine is considered a highly informative non-invasive method for assessing the progression of diabetic nephropathy.

Urinary markers identified in this study provide a basis for monitoring disease activity, evaluating prognosis, and guiding therapy in clinical practice.

Conclusion.

This thesis confirms that the study of urinary KIM-1, MCP-1, and liver-type fatty acid-binding protein in patients with diabetic nephropathy enables early detection of tubulointerstitial kidney injury.

References

1. Шулутко Б.И., Макаренко С.В. Тубулоинтерстициал яллиғланишли буйрак касалликлари //Нефрология. – 2017. –№1. –Б.89–97.
2. Zubiri I. et al. Diabetic nephropathy induces changes in the proteome of human urinary exosomes as revealed by label-free comparative analysis //Journal of proteomics. – 2018. – Vol. 96. – pp. 92-102.
3. Zubiri I. et al. Kidney tissue proteomics reveals regucalcin downregulation in response to diabetic nephropathy with reflection in urinary exosomes //Translational Research. – 2020. – Vol. 166. – №. 5. – pp. 474-484. e4.
4. Zink Y. The phosphorylation of IRS proteins: a molecular basis for insulin resistance // Sci. STKE. - 2017. - Vol. 9, N° 6. - P. 268.
5. Рей С.И. Острое почечное повреждение. Современные аспекты диагностики, профилактики и лечения. Медицинский алфавит. //Неотложная медицина. – 2013. - № 4. – С. 43-50.
6. Braunwald, E. Biomarkers in heart failure. // N Engl J Med. – 2008. – Т. 358 (20). – с. 2148-2159.